

Toward a CCS Observatory

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A common message communicated at the end of any report on the creative and cultural sector (CCS) is that the insights are limited by the availability of data, and what is needed is a Cultural Observatory. It is an issue that is widely agreed upon that more data is needed; and that aggregating as many possible sources would be the best idea. Whilst we agree with the sentiment, it is argued here that the particular challenges of the CCS mean that we have to take a more nuanced approach: rather than simply 'more data', we need more relevant data; moreover, we should ask 'relevant for what'?

We do have a lot of information about the CCS, and we have been confident enough of its general scope to make a strong case to regions, nations and the EU for a refocused recognition of the CCS, both linked to the definition and concept (beyond either the traditional not for profit culture, and commercial culture), and associated with the scale and growth indicated by this data the need for this to be represented in policy.

The various 'mapping' exercises by nation states and the EU in the early 2000s introduced the field of the CCS to those previously unfamiliar with it, it seemed to be a very positive story. However, they also provoked more uncomfortable questions about precisely how, and why, the CCS might be supported. These questions took the debate about the CCS beyond the old debates about the support of culture as a 'good thing', and towards questions of how growth, development and innovation could be supported; moreover, if the same generic policy tools adopted, say for

car making or chemicals, would be suitable for the CCS. It is at this point that researchers became aware of the need for more information and understanding of the CCS related to the unique organisation and processes that they present.

The challenge for data, specifically for the data regularly collected by Eurostat is first, that there is little information of organisation and process, and the nature of change. Second, there is an historic challenge to the way we classify industry, rooted in the expectations of mid-twentieth century economies. Again, the challenge of the CCS is that it is an outlier that has led change. The net result is that many of the transformations of the CCS have not been visible in the industry classifications; for good reason, industries like the computer games simply did not exist before the 1990s. To develop a robust time series of data means minimal changes to classifications, and careful coordination across territories and data collection agencies.

Beyond the classifications of industries and occupations, which have been revised and updated, but not quick enough for the CCS, and not in sufficient detail. The overarching organisational change in the CCS has been driven by digitisation, and this registers in headline growth. However, much of that transformation has occurred in a process of dis-and re-intermediation: literally the break-up of large monopoly employers and their replacement by an agile network of new intermediaries and many freelance, sole operators and project-based organisations. This is a major cause of the data lacuna. Moreover, it is not one easy to fill, as the units are so small, and evade the periodicity of data collection.

Layered on top of these issues are the complex new hybrid CCS activities that work across the cultural and not

for profit, and commercial and economic focused activities. Again, our inherited data collection based upon the firm division of commercial and non-commercial culture, or those activities where visitor numbers were used as a proxy for 'output'. Finally, in this list of problems we can point to place-based employment data that does not illustrate the flows of goods and services (material, and especially immaterial) across production systems (between ideas, making, distribution, exchange, and archiving).

Logically, there is a solution here: more data collection. However, the cost would be high and length of time to complete such a recalibrated system would be long; and we need to know now. As noted above, the right sort of data is also qualified by 'for what purposes'? We can note another dimension to our problem that whilst the supply of data has more or less remained static, the demand has shifted. Industries and publics who use CCS goods and services (and this is expanding to the whole economy now), industry stakeholder bodies such as trade associations, cities, and regions. All these parties need a more nuanced understanding evaluation and interpretation of the CCS.

The CICERONE project, which is a pioneer example of research looking at whole production networks in the CCS, offers some insights into how we might modify our information collection approaches to the CCS. The approach based upon this 'production cycle' idea we need to extend a step further, to recognise the spatial and organisational characteristics of 'extended cultural production'. Simply this requires us to follow the supply chains around the cycle. Previously, we worked with an assumption that many cultural activities were rooted in place and locally created and consumed; today, the cultural sector reflects the complex concentration and dispersal of a network of cultural intermediaries which may or may

not be concentrated. Clearly, questions about co-location are important, and have been a key concern of policy makers, but in production networks the question of who controls the 'switching points' of networks, so that they can operate as gatekeepers is critical: it affects price, and market access. We argue that by being ignorant of this network configuration of power and control of networks we are entering the policy debate unarmed. Again, this notion, of Global Production Networks, that has replaced the simple ideas and practice of monopoly or multinational corporation, or even platform can be found (and is recognised) in other industries yet it has been relatively obscured in the CCS.

The project, in proposing a Pilot CCS Observatory begins sketching out an alternative to 'more is better', arguing instead for quality and use. Aggregating more of the same data will not show us what and how things have changes, it will not give us insight into newness and innovation. This is not such a novel problem, all industries face this challenge, but the problem is acute in the CCS due to the paucity of basic data on industries/ domains of activity, and partial coverage of the production functions. This is why we argue that a necessary foundation for a CCS observatory of a clear conception of the CCS. The relatively new definition of the CCS is more like an aggregation of activities that fall under the culture umbrella; what is lacking is measurement and appreciation of the production functions. As noted above, historically this have been better measured in traditional industries, but under reported in cultural ones.

This is why we argue for the need for not simply a CCS observatory, but a new type of observatory that is able to engage in insight and foresight activities, drawing upon a range of stakeholders and complementary information

sources. Both this will help to calibrate out view from the published statistical record, and to alert us to new trends and new places to look for information.

The CICERONE test pilot observatory is based upon the innovative study of CCS production systems, and the common configurations of them in a 2 x 2 matrix: either controlled locally or internationally; and, governed hierarchically or horizontally. This has allowed us to create a provisional new 'lens' through which to view the CCS; something that helps us to augment the existing statistical data with richer qualitative accounts of how production systems operate. Obviously, for a limited academic project only a limited number of production networks could be mapped, but we are confident that we have a first approximation of the major types of networks. And the mapping could be continued and extended to develop the robustness of the classification system.

We can illustrate typical production networks and point out the different dynamics of power and control in each. Moreover, we can explore the various spatial different styles of spatial footprint, what and where different production functions are involved and when and where they take place, and what mode of governance dominates the network. The observatory also allows a deep dive into the interviews of the actors in these networks, and we offer a comment on the types of policies that are likely to be effective in addressing them.

Our first point is an important one, that we discovered that there was not one ideal type of production system type for the CCS, but many; and the configurations of this affect the 'power geometry' of the network, and how and where effective policy interventions might take place. To simplify matters we have reduced the network types into a two-by-two table based on scale and control: scale

between international and local; and control between vertical and horizontal. We have classified the different industries we surveyed and classified them, however, we found that there was further difference by the way that 'business models' were interpreted. Simply, that the notion of a business model in the CCS allows for the complementary maximisation of cultural, economic, and social values.

Critically, using our investigative insights and information we have been able to offer a richer insight into the nodes and flows of CCS production networks. We have of course produced the usual 'industry' reports, however, our key innovation was to shift to the lens of the network. We have coded our qualitative interview material so that each network relation can be recalled and examined by case study quotation. In this way, we allow the exploration and elaboration of not only the shape and type of networks, but what it means to work in these networks and where the power and control lies. These insights add a vital complement and depth to the (sometimes) patchy statistical coverage.

This central idea of a coherent conceptual, and empirical mapping of the production systems, and a means to recall and report it we think adds a step toward a new type of CCS Observatory. It enables the comparison of both the quantitative and the qualitative lenses to provide a more subtle insight into a fast-changing sector; moreover, it provides a new pivot for policy making based on whole production networks (not single firms).

Of course, this is simply the first step in re-building and remaking our vision and understanding of the CCS; as such this is an important demonstration, a proof of concept, what a refined CCS observatory (core) could be, not simply bigger (quantitatively or aggregated), but more relevant

(qualitative and process focused). Clearly, what we gain in depth is not matched by our aspiration of breadth too. That requires further steps beyond this pilot demonstration project.

First, we need to build out and develop the range of case studies that the project is based upon; it is not the issue that because it is a case study that it is limiting but how representative it is of a particular typology. This is a pragmatic process of refinement which can always be improved.

Second, the vision and lens of the CCS that we offer highlights more clearly where the weakness of our current data and understandings of the CCS are. Obviously, we have pointed to the organisational dimensions, but the process and flow is another critical one. A lot of data is in existence of these flows; however, it is either locked behind paywalls, or resides within the limits of commercial sensitivity. Here is a vital role for trade associations and public bodies to negotiate on how it is possible to get more of these immaterial trade flows visible and in the public domain. In some cases, it will simply be the calibration of time-sensitiveness, in other cases more complex masking may be required.

The existence of more and better data can be seen as an end in itself; however, we have argued here that a key aim should be to make the information relevant to all stakeholders. This can have strategic benefits for individual industries or places. Many micro-CCS businesses trade on their innovation or speed to market, to make up for poor intelligence; improved market intelligence and enhanced foresight intelligence based upon such foundations could generate a strategic advantage and build a more strategic industry perspective.

Looked at more widely, other industries are able to

mobilise parallel insights to appeal to politicians and policy makers for support and alert the same agencies to near future challenges. At present the CCS industries are hampered in their ability to engage in this vital dialogue, as the information base that they rely upon is not adequate to communicate these messages.

More about the CICERONE project can be found here: <https://cicerone-project.eu>

The CICERONE pilot CCS observatory can be found here: <http://www.ccs-observatory.eu>